

Mars, among latest? Tendency to gossip, group cohesiveness, and work motivation of teaching personnel in selected schools in Bacoor

Winterson C. Ambion

Abstract

Since the onset of the recent pandemic, the concept of Marites has surged in popularity, becoming a part of the vibrant language of contemporary Filipino culture. In a generation strongly shaped by social media, *Marites* represents the quintessential 'chismosa', which has evolved from its original meaning as an idle talk about the personal affairs of others to the act of identifying someone who engages in such behavior in the workplace. The present study aims to determine the interrelationship between the tendency to gossip, work motivation, and group cohesiveness of teaching personnel. 58 participants were recruited from selected private educational institutions in Bacoor City, Cavite, Philippines. The sample consisted of 10 males (17.24%) and 48 females (82.76%), whose mean age was 36.07 years ($SD = 13.52$). Results of the Pearson r analysis revealed that while the respondents' tendency to gossip and their work motivation have a low positive correlation ($r = 0.36$), such a relationship is statistically significant ($p = .01$). Meanwhile, the former variable obtained a negligible correlation with group cohesiveness ($r = 0.017$), which is not significant as well ($p = 0.89$). Furthermore, significant differences in the respondents' tendency to gossip in terms of gender and family structure were revealed.

Keywords: Group cohesiveness; Tendency to gossip; Work motivation.

Winterson C. Ambion*

Quality Assurance and Institutional Effectiveness Office, St. Dominic College of Asia, Bacoor City, Cavite, Philippines
 E-mail: wcambion@sdca.edu.ph / ambionw@gmail.com

*Corresponding author

To cite this article:

Ambion, W. C. (2024). Mars, among latest? Tendency to gossip, group cohesiveness, and work motivation of teaching personnel in selected schools in Bacoor. *SDCA Asia-Pacific Multidisciplinary Research Journal*, 6(1), 9-15.

doi: 10.5281/zenodo.12792482

Introduction

"*Marites*" is a clipped word for the phrase "*Mars, Among Latest?*", which is a personification of a widely held concept of gossip ("*tsismis*") in the Filipino culture that became most popular during the onset of the COVID-19 pandemic. Remarkably, gossip has long been associated with women, a trend that has its roots in Anglo-American culture, where gossip first acquired a gender-specific connotation. Thus, the term 'Marites', a common Filipina name, became a human embodiment of any person who engages in gossip, rumor mongering, and other similar activities.

According to Foster (2004), gossip is characterized by the sharing of information with a judgmental tone about people who are not present. It is something that many people do often. Gossip is frequently seen as vile and untrustworthy conduct and is denounced as a norm breach in practically all cultures. It is defined here as the informal exchange of evaluations about absent third parties (Dores Cruz et al., 2019). Despite this generally unfavorable impression, some academics contend that individuals like gossip in particular and spend an enormous amount of conversational time doing it. Several recent experimental laboratory studies have shown that the motivation for gossip is the desire to shield others from those who disregard cooperative norms. Moreover, these studies show that when groups gossip, or even just when the potential for gossip exists, this discourages group members from acting selfishly, as shown by an increase in donations to partners, offers in dictator games, and participation in public goods dilemmas (Wu et al., 2018).

Assumptions of the Study

The aim of the present study is to determine the relationship among gossiping tendency, group cohesiveness, and work motivation among teaching personnel in a private educational institution in Bacoor City, Cavite. Specifically, the researcher seeks to focus on the psychosocial pros and cons of gossiping behavior in the context of an organization.

Dunbar (2004) stated, from an evolutionary standpoint, that gossip may have been advantageous since it fosters social relationships. It has also been suggested that it was selected because it aids in preventing norm violations in groups. Throughout the course of evolution, people grew increasingly social because it afforded them safety and the opportunity to share resources. A single individual cannot repel a bear or capture a mammoth, but a group can. Sociality was particularly advantageous for the evolution of *Homo sapiens*, but there was one caveat: Although society as a whole benefits best when all members participate equally, it is tempting for individuals to not contribute and yet gain the advantages of the efforts of others.

Research Problem

The assumptions on this study are further strengthened by the increasing evidence from the current body of literature across scientific fields that suggests that gossip may actually be beneficial for groups. Specifically, the researcher seeks to answer the following questions:

1. Is there a significant difference on the respondents' gossiping tendency when grouped according to their sociodemographic profile?
2. Is there a significant relationship between the respondents' tendency to gossip, group cohesiveness, and their work motivation?

Significance of the Study

The current study helps us gain a thorough grasp of gossip in groups' advantages and disadvantages. The following four contributions to the field of study are ones the researcher would want to make.

1. Demonstrate that the perspective of the respondents can provide insight into both positive and negative aspects of gossip, particularly in an organizational context.
2. Provide current insights of the cultural antecedents and motivations of gossip as a Filipino trait and its impact to the broader society.
3. Increase understanding of the sociodemographic factors that give rise to gossiping behavior, thus spreading awareness and minimizing gender-based prejudices.
4. Contribute to the growing body of psychological research on Filipino cultural traits that shall promote better understanding of '*kapwa*' or fellows.

When considered collectively, the findings would show that gossip has both a negative and a positive impact on a group and that the outcome depends on both situational variables (such as who is the recipient of the gossip and whether it is true or false) and agent perspectives (such as being the target or the observer of gossip).

Scope and Limitation of the Study

The study focused mainly on the relationships among the tendency to gossip, work motivation, and group cohesiveness. The collection of data was distributed randomly to selected educational institutions in Bacoor City, Cavite, which include St. Dominic College of Asia, Statefields School, Inc., and STI College-Bacoor. Respondents were composed of teaching personnel who handle students from senior high school to college in a regular or full-time capacity. This means that part-time teachers were excluded from this study. The survey questionnaires were disseminated to the respondents by means of a Google Form, which was composed of a consent form, a profile checklist, and three (3) validated survey questionnaires. The duration of data collection was completed in almost two (2) months, from April to May 2023.

Theoretical Framework

Dunbar's Theory of Language Development

We spend a significant amount of time as humans communicating with one another through speech. Most of this time is also spent conversing with one another regarding one another. Roughly sixty-five percent (65%) of the time, we discuss various societal issues (Dunbar, 2004). The amount of time that is spent engaging in all of this gossip suggests that it must serve some sort of purpose in our society.

According to the theory of the development of language proposed by Robin Dunbar (1997), the ability of humans to engage in gossip is what enables them to maintain social coherence in extremely large groups, and the selection pressure to do so is what drove the evolution of language in the first place. According to this view, prior to the time when humans started to gossip, something else must have been the glue that held our communities together. Grooming is the mechanism that is most likely to be a possibility because it is still used by other primates. Not only does this help people maintain their personal hygiene, but it also serves a vital societal purpose. The giving and receiving of grooming paves the way for the establishment and upkeep of group hierarchies, the formation of alliances, and the expression of apologies (Seyfarth & Cheney, 1993).

So, for other primates, grooming functions as an extremely efficient form of social glue. The only drawback is that maintaining social relationships through grooming requires a significant investment of time in settings where there are a large number of people present. The amount of time that primates spend grooming increases in proportion to the number of individuals in a group (Dunbar, 2004). This is due to the fact that larger group sizes generate more ecological competition, which results in local food sources being depleted at a faster rate. This results in battles, which increases the significance of forming strong alliances. But the efficiency of a coalition is directly proportional to the amount of time each member of the coalition spends cultivating and improving themselves (Dunbar, 2004).

Despite the significant progress that has been made, the academic research on gossip in companies is not yet complete, particularly the research on the consequences of perceived negative workplace gossip on the conduct of the target in their work-related activities.

The researcher seeks to explore the possibility that while gossiping behavior carries a negative connotation, this construct may also yield positive psychosocial gains in group cohesiveness and work motivation. Teaching personnel were preferred to be respondents to this research due to the premise that "teacher gossip" has been scientifically documented. In fact, research demonstrating how prevalent it has grown was published in 2009 by the Journal of Contemporary Ethnography (Hallett et al., 2009).

Abraham Maslow's Hierarchy of Needs

A useful framework for evaluating work motivation among teaching staff is provided by Maslow's Hierarchy of Needs. Physiological demands are the most basic and must be met. This involves making certain that educators are paid fairly, have enough time off, and have suitable working environments so they can focus on their profession without being distracted by unsatisfied basic requirements (Maslow, 1943).

When physiological needs are met, safety needs take priority. It is crucial to have a secure job, favorable working circumstances, and advantages like health insurance. Because they do not have to worry about losing their employment or working in dangerous conditions, teachers who are secure in their jobs have a greater motivation (Maslow, 1943). They are able to devote more of themselves to their teaching duties because they feel secure. Esteem needs include being recognized and respected. Teachers are more motivated when they receive recognition for their work through promotions, awards, and positive feedback (Maslow, 1943). Teachers motivated by opportunities for personal growth and engaging in challenging work feel more fulfilled and productive (Maslow, 1943).

Maslow's Hierarchy of Needs suggests that social needs, such as the need for acceptance and belonging, foster social interactions and make an inclusive culture in terms of group cohesiveness. Group cohesiveness is enhanced in teachers when they build meaningful relationships and have a sense of belonging within their team. This promotes better collaboration and a more peaceful work environment (Maslow, 1943).

When teachers are given opportunities to realize their full potential within the team, they are more likely to engage deeply with their work and their colleagues. Teams that support individual growth and encourage creativity and innovation create an environment where members feel fulfilled and motivated to contribute their best efforts (Maslow, 1943).

Conceptual Paradigm

The researcher assumes that relationships among gossiping tendencies, group cohesiveness, and work motivation among teaching personnel exist and can be discovered. Some literature links gossiping behavior as a characteristic more commonly associated with women. Nonetheless, the current study aims to explore the assumption that such constructs may not be exclusively tied to a specific gender. Similarly, the paper further seeks to find out whether certain sociodemographic factors such as age, family structure, and average monthly income give rise to the respondents' propensity to engage in gossiping behavior.

Figure 1. A conceptual paradigm illustrating the sociodemographic factors that influence the respondents' tendency to gossip and its correlations with group cohesiveness and work motivation.

Methodology

Research Method

The researcher utilized a correlational approach to investigate whether the variables significantly correlate with each other. The researcher might determine whether variables have a positive, negative, or no relationship by utilizing correlational analysis. Understanding the fundamental reasons for some phenomena or forecasting future events might both benefit from this information. Conversely, comparative analyses were utilized to determine the significant differences between the respondents' socio-demographic characteristics and their tendency for gossip. The ability to compare and contrast two or more variables is an essential aspect of comparative analysis, which is a valuable research tool. It makes it possible to identify relationships, trends, and patterns that would not be visible using other techniques.

Participants

The target sample population consisted of teaching personnel aged twenty-five (25) to sixty (60) years old, which is the normative age range of teachers from entry level to retirement. They must be currently employed in a private institution in Cavite and have earned at least one (1) academic year of experience in teaching students at the senior high school or tertiary level. The requirement is taken into consideration because, when compared to their more experienced colleagues, rookie instructors are less likely to indulge in gossip because they are still attempting to make their mark in their current position and may not want to take the chance of ruining their reputation by gossiping. Additionally, they could be more concerned with figuring out what their job requires and fostering relationships with colleagues.

Table 1. Sociodemographic characteristics of the respondents (N = 58)

Demographic variables	Male		Female		Total	
Number	10 (17.24%)		48 (82.76%)		58 (100%)	
Age (M ± SD)	42 ± 15.62		34.83 ± 12.88		36.07 ± 13.52	
Average Monthly Income	<i>f</i>	%	<i>f</i>	%	<i>f</i>	%
Below 10,000 pesos	4	6.90	6	10.34	10	17.24
10,001 to 20,000 pesos	0	0.00	8	13.79	8	13.79
20,001 to 30,000 pesos	0	0.00	12	20.69	12	20.69
30,001 to 40,000 pesos	6	10.34	2	3.45	8	13.79
More than 40,000 pesos	0	0.00	20	34.48	20	34.48
Total	10	17.24	48	82.76	58	100
Family Structure	<i>f</i>	%	<i>f</i>	%	<i>f</i>	%
Living as a solo parent	0	0.00	8	13.79	8	13.79
Living with a spouse and children	2	3.45	10	17.24	12	20.69
Living solely with a spouse	2	3.45	3	5.17	5	8.62
Living with extended family members	6	10.34	21	36.21	27	46.55
Living with parents or guardians only	0	0.00	6	10.34	6	10.34
Total	10	17.24	48	82.76	58	100.00

Table 1 presents the sociodemographic characteristics of the respondents. As illustrated, out of 58 respondents, 48 (82.76%) are females and 10 (17.24%) are males. In terms of average monthly income, 10 (17.24%) of the respondents earn a monthly income below 10,000 pesos; 8 (13.79%) earn 10,001 to 20,000 pesos; 12 (20.69%) earn 20,001 to 30,000 pesos; 8 (13.79%) earn 30,001 to 40,000 pesos; and 20 (34.48%) earn more than 40,000 pesos. Moreover, the majority of the respondents live together with their extended family, which comprises 30 (52%) of the total sample. Subsequently, 14 (24%) live with their spouse and children; 8 (14%) live as solo parents; and 6 (10%) are living solely with their parents or guardians.

Instruments

The **Tendency to Gossip Questionnaire (TGQ)** is a 20-item survey instrument that was developed by Nevo et al. (1993). The scores on the TGQ were normally distributed and showed a good level of internal consistency (.87) for a sample size of 120 respondents (58 female, 62 male) in a local sample. The TGQ subscales are as follows: (1) physical appearance; (2) achievement; (3) social information; and (4) sublimated gossip.

Motivation at Work Scale (MAWS) by Gagné et al. (2010) is an 8-item survey questionnaire that was made in line with self-determination theory's idea that motivation has many different aspects. The instrument used a 7-point scale: 1 for "not at all," 2 for "very little," 3 for "a little," 4 for "moderately," 5 for "strong," 6 for "very strong," and 7 for "exactly" to show how much the respondents currently match one of the reasons why they do their specific job. Alpha coefficient subscales show that only two of the eight alpha coefficients are below the standard of .80 when piloted to a local sample, but the rest have met the standard of .70.

Group Cohesiveness Scale (GCS) by Klocek et al. (2020). The ordinal confirmatory factor analysis (CFA) validated a two-dimensional solution in the English version of the scale, which has strong psychometric qualities (RMSEA = 0.075; TLI = 0.986). The study showed that there are two categories of group cohesiveness— affective and behavioral—that are moderately to highly related ($r = 0.79$). Up to the level of factor means, the two-dimensional model remained invariant across genders, ages, educational levels, and time (retest after six weeks). Both the emotional and behavioral domains' internal consistency ratings were good (affective, 0.86; behavioral, 0.81).

Data Collection Procedure

Upon selecting the appropriate test instruments for measuring the variables, the researcher sent a letter of permission to the respective authors of each standard questionnaire to utilize, modify, and, if necessary, subject those instruments to pilot testing to suit the needs of the target sample population of the present study.

Similarly, while the completion of the validation process was ongoing, the researcher sent a communication letter to the respective school administrators of selected educational institutions in Cavite. The letter discussed the nature, purpose, risks involved, confidentiality matters, methodology, and potential benefits of the study to the institutions. The researcher also requested referrals from the selected schools to identify willing participants to answer the questionnaires.

Once permission was granted, the researcher allotted a period of fifteen to twenty (15 to 20) days to gather participants who were willing and eligible to be included in the study. Ethical considerations, such as privacy and confidentiality, were duly noted. Once informed consent was obtained from each participant, the researcher disseminated the personal data sheet together with the three (3) standard questionnaires, either in printed or digital form, whichever was more convenient to the respondents. Twenty-nine (29) responses were collected through Google Forms, while thirty-five (35) were gathered through printed survey forms, six (6) of which were discarded by the researcher because some respondents did not meet the inclusion criteria.

Ethical Considerations

To comply with ethical considerations in conducting research, the researcher has obtained respondents' consent to answer the survey questionnaires, which is expected to cause no physical or emotional harm to the respondents involved in the research. The study's purpose and process were explained to the participants in detail in order for them to be given the freedom to voluntarily agree or disagree to join the study. They were also informed that should they wish to withdraw at any point during the period of answering the survey, they could do so. This is to ensure respect for human dignity. Furthermore, respondents were made fully aware that their information would be handled with the utmost confidentiality and anonymity. All the data that was gathered from the respondents will be secure and by no means disclosed.

Data Analysis

In the present study, multiple correlational analyses were used in order to determine whether or not a relationship exists between the variables being studied and, if one does, to ascertain the magnitude and direction of that relationship. In this study, multiple correlations will demonstrate whether or not a relationship exists among the respondents' work motivation, group cohesiveness, and their propensity to engage in gossiping behavior. Furthermore, tests of significant difference using a t-test (for gender) and an ANOVA (analysis of variance) were performed to determine whether the tendency to gossip will vary when respondents are grouped in terms of different sociodemographic factors such as age, family structure, and average monthly income.

Results

Question 1: Is there a significant difference with the respondents' gossiping tendency when grouped according to the sociodemographic factors?

Table 2. ANOVA Results (Age-Range)

Source of Variation	SS	df	MS	F	P-value	F crit
Between Groups	2903.089	3	967.696	1.856	0.148	2.776
Within Groups	28152.635	54	521.345			
Total	31055.724	57				

Table 2 presents the results of the analysis of variance in the age range. As illustrated above, since the p-value of 0.15 is higher than the significance level of 0.05, the researcher failed to reject the null hypothesis and conclude that there is no significant difference in the respondents' tendency to gossip when grouped according to age range.

Table 3. t-Test Results (Gender)

Gender	Observations	Mean	P-value	Interpretation	Decision
Male	10	44.2	0.021	The result is significant at p < .05 level of significance	Reject Null Hypothesis
Female	48	59.58			

Table 3 presents the results of the t-test on gender. As illustrated above, since the p-value of 0.021 is less than the significance level of 0.05, the researcher decides to reject the null hypothesis and conclude that there is a significant difference between the respondents' tendency to gossip when grouped according to gender. Therefore, this result revealed that female respondents have a higher tendency to engage in gossip than their male counterparts.

Table 4. ANOVA Results (Average Monthly Income)

Source of Variation	SS	df	MS	F	P-value	F crit
Between Groups	1300.424	4	325.106	0.579	0.679	2.546
Within Groups	29755.3	53	561.421			
Total	31055.724	57				

Table 4 presents the results of the analysis of variance on average monthly income. As illustrated above, since the p-value of 0.68 is higher than the significance level of 0.05, the researcher failed to reject the null hypothesis and conclude that there is no significant difference in the respondents' tendency to gossip when grouped according to their average monthly income.

Table 5. ANOVA Results (Family Structure)

Source of Variation	SS	df	MS	F	P-value	F crit
Between Groups	6482.434	4	1620.608	3.552	0.012	2.543
Within Groups	24637.295	54	456.246			
Total	31119.729	58				

Table 5 presents the results of the analysis of variance in family structure. As illustrated above, since the p-value of 0.02 is less than the significance level of 0.05, the researcher decides to reject the null hypothesis and conclude that there is a significant difference in the respondents' tendency to gossip when grouped according to their family structure type.

Question 2: Is there a significant relationship between respondents' group cohesiveness with their co-workers and their tendency to gossip?

Table 6 presents the results of the correlations among tendencies to gossip, work motivation, and group cohesiveness. The results revealed no significant relationship between the tendency to gossip and group cohesiveness.

However, work motivation significantly correlates with both the tendency to gossip and cohesiveness at the $p < 0.05$ level of significance.

Table 6. Correlation Results (Tendency to Gossip and Work Motivation; N = 58)

Variables	M	SD	1	2
Tendency to Gossip	56.93	23.34		
Work Motivation	52.34	15.25	*0.34 (.01)	
Group Cohesiveness	31.31	7.48	0.02 (0.90)	*0.41 (.00)

Discussion

Gender Differences in the Tendency to Gossip

Apparently, the concept of Marites has been fondly attributed to women who habitually engage in gossip and parodied on social media wearing a loose-fitting duster dress and a towel over their wet hair. Gender differences in the perception of the tendency to gossip are very strong in modern Filipino society. In only a short period of time, the concept of "marites" has become a well-known way to describe people who talk about other people at work. There is a great deal of study on how women talk in the workplace, but there is a lack of study on how men talk about other people. Many of these studies show that women gossip more than men (Farley et al., 2010).

Men who gossip are seen as merely socializing in Filipino society, which may be viewed more positively than their female counterparts who engage in the same behavior. The general belief that men gossip less may be attributable to this more favorable interpretation of gossip. Although the results showed that both men and women gossiped, the current study found that women were more likely to gossip than men. This result is consistent with the findings of Davis et al. (2018), who found that women reported more of a tendency to gossip than men, especially regarding physical appearance and social information, while men reported more of a tendency to gossip regarding achievement. Women also reported more satisfaction and value from gossiping than men did.

Family Structure and Tendency to Gossip

The results of the current study suggest that respondents who either live together with a spouse or partner or live as a solo parent will have a higher tendency to gossip than those who live together with both a spouse or partner and children. This further suggests that those who live together with their extended family are less likely to engage in gossiping behavior. Rözer et al. (2016) found that people who spend a lot of time with their families may not have as much time for their friends. Since Filipinos are known for their strong and close family ties, they tend to favor kin who are much more inclined to come to our help when we need help than anyone else, even if these are close friends. This is because people may unconsciously choose to have interaction with either family or friends (Homans, 1958; Johnson & Leslie, 1982). Consequently, people from large families tend to prioritize their family relationships over those with their friends (Dunbar, 1990). The researchers behind the study hypothesize that those with a reduced demand for connection and socializing are less likely to engage in workplace gossip.

Tendency to Gossip and Work Motivation

Since the workplace is where most people spend their time outside of their homes, it makes sense that it would be a hub for spreading rumors, and indeed, workplace gossip has become the primary informal channel for sharing information within an organization (Yan & Zhang, 2021). Those who have been on the receiving end of workplace gossip tend to have an adverse perception of the practice as a whole. Recent studies have shown that there are some advantages to workplace gossip as well as disadvantages (Yue et al., 2015). Therefore, it is crucial to linked theories and practices that the good and adverse consequences of workplace gossip be thoroughly discussed. The current research found a weak but statistically significant positive relationship between gossiping tendencies and workplace motivation. This indicates that the two variables tend to increase in unison with one another, although the significance of this correlation may depend on other factors.

The social comparison theory states that when workers engage in workplace gossip, they will inevitably draw parallels between themselves and the rumor's subject matter. Employees will become self-aware of their weaknesses when they compare their own conduct and performance at work to that of a "gossip goal" and discover that it falls short of expectations. Employees will be highly motivated to maintain or increase their behavioral performance in line with the gossip aim (Grosser et al., 2010) and to show high levels of work enthusiasm. Recent research, however, suggests that only constructive gossip spread around the office can boost morale, whereas negative gossip can have the opposite effect (Yan & Zhang, 2021).

Tendency to Gossip and Group Cohesiveness

Gossip, according to Rajačić and colleagues (2020), is an integral part of social life and plays a significant role in the most important social processes, such as the upkeep of groups and social cohesiveness. However, the present research shows that there is no significant relationship between gossiping and group cohesiveness. Previous studies have shown that gossip is a social connection system used to create a sense of community among people who may not otherwise interact with one another, to penalize those who break group norms, and even to coerce others by inspiring the dread of the gossipers themselves. However, no direct empirical research investigates the hypothesis that talking negatively about individuals leads to greater cooperation on the part of those who benefit (De Backer et al., 2016).

Conclusion and Recommendations

Findings showed that women were more inclined than men to engage in gossip. Women are more likely than men to communicate their feelings and to participate in stronger relationships with others, which could help to explain this. But it is important to keep in mind that gossiping can harm relationships and individuals. It could lead to rumors, upset emotions, and damage to one's reputation. Therefore, it is imperative that individuals remain careful with both their words and actions when interacting with others. Even though gossip is a tendency for both men and women, it is critical that people recognize the possible negative effects of gossip and seek to improve their communication skills.

Moreover, those who have less desire for social engagement and connection are less likely to spread gossip. This gossip causes the absence of a persistent need for approval or attention from others. Gossip is a common tool used by people to establish connections with one another; however, those who are not very interested in forming social bonds may not find it useful. Individuals who have greater introversion or less extraversion often engage in introspection and reflection. They have the option to be alone themselves or join in activities that are exclusive to others. Therefore, people could be less likely to gossip when it goes against their values or interests.

The practice of gossiping is common and has been observed in many different social circles. It is a widely held belief that gossiping promotes cohesiveness within a group by strengthening relationships between its members. That being said, this assumption may not always be accurate. Gossip can create a hostile and mistrustful environment within a group. It could lead to false impressions and rumors that incite resentment among the members of the group. Ultimately, this could weaken relationships between people and lessen the sense of unity of the group as a whole. Moreover, gossip frequently involves talking badly about someone behind their back, which can cause hurt and feelings of betrayal. As a result, some can feel excluded and opt to walk away from the group entirely. In conclusion, even though gossiping could appear like a harmless way to foster relationships with others, it can actually have a negative effect on group cohesion. Groups should put more effort into developing strong relationships through open communication and respect for one another rather than participating in gossip.

The Need for Further Research

Gossip is a conventional thing that has been going on for hundreds of years. It is a way of sharing information about other people, usually without their knowledge or permission. Gossip can be interesting and even enlightening at times, but it can also hurt people and break up relationships. More study needs to be done on gossip to learn more about how it affects people and society as a whole. Studies have shown that gossiping can make people feel bad things like anxiety, sadness, and a low sense of self-worth. It can also hurt relationships and identities, making people feel alone and shut out of society. By learning more about gossip, we can come up with ways to reduce its bad effects while keeping the good things about communication. This could involve teaching people about how gossip hurts people or coming up with ways to help people deal with the bad effects of being talked about. In the end, more study needs to be done on gossip to fully understand how it affects people and society. By doing these things, we can work toward making the world a better place for everyone.

References

- Davis, A. C., Dufort, C., Desrochers, J., Vaillancourt, T., & Arnocky, S. (2018). Gossip as an intrasexual competition strategy: Sex differences in gossip frequency, content, and attitudes. *Evolutionary Psychological Science*, 4, 141-153. <https://doi.org/10.1007/s40806-017-0121-9>

- De Backer, C. J., Larson, C., Fisher, M. L., McAndrew, F. T., & Rudnicki, K. (2016). When strangers start to gossip: Investigating the effect of gossip on cooperation in a prisoner's dilemma game. *Evolutionary Psychological Science*, 2(4), 268-277. <https://doi.org/10.1007/s40806-016-0063-7>
- Dores Cruz, T. D., Beersma, B., Dijkstra, M. T., & Bechtoldt, M. N. (2019). The bright and dark side of gossip for cooperation in groups. *Frontiers in Psychology*, 10, 1374. <https://doi.org/10.3389/fpsyg.2019.01374>
- Dunbar, R. (1997). *Grooming, gossip, and the evolution of language*. Harvard University Press.
- Dunbar, R. I. M. (2004). Gossip in evolutionary perspective. *Review of General Psychology*, 8(2), 100-110. <https://doi.org/10.1037/1089-2680.8.2.100>
- Farley, S. D., Timme, D. R., & Hart, J. W. (2010). On coffee talk and break-room chatter: Perceptions of women who gossip in the workplace. *The Journal of Social Psychology*, 150(4), 361-368. <https://doi.org/10.1080/00224540903365430>
- Foster, E. K. (2004). Research on gossip: Taxonomy, methods, and future directions. *Review of General Psychology*, 8(2), 78-99. <https://doi.org/10.1037/1089-2680.8.2.78>
- Gagné, M., Forest, J., Gilbert, M. H., Aubé, C., Morin, E., & Malorni, A. (2010). The motivation at work scale: Validation evidence in two languages. *Educational and Psychological Measurement*, 70(4), 628-646. <https://doi.org/10.1177/0013164409355698>
- Grosser, T. J., Lopez-Kidwell, V., & Labianca, G. (2010). A social network analysis of positive and negative gossip in organizational life. *Group & Organization Management*, 35(2), 177-212. <https://doi.org/10.1177/1059601109360391>
- Hallett, T., Harger, B., & Eder, D. (2009). Gossip at work: Unsanctioned evaluative talk in formal school meetings. *Journal of Contemporary Ethnography*, 38(5), 584-618. <https://doi.org/10.1177/0891241609342117>
- Homans, G. C. (1958). Social behavior as exchange. *American Journal of Sociology*, 63(6), 597-606. <https://doi.org/10.1086/222355>
- Johnson, M. P., & Leslie, L. (1982). Couple involvement and network structure: A test of the dyadic withdrawal hypothesis. *Social Psychology Quarterly*, 45(1), 34-43. <https://doi.org/10.2307/3033672>
- Klocek, A., Řiháček, T., & Cígler, H. (2020). Psychometric evaluation of the Czech version of group cohesiveness scale (GCS) in a clinical sample: A two-dimensional model. *Frontiers in Psychology*, 11, 595651. <https://doi.org/10.3389/fpsyg.2020.595651>
- Maslow, A. H. (1943). A theory of human motivation. *Psychological Review*, 50(4), 370-396. <https://psycnet.apa.org/record/1943-03751-001>
- Nevo, O., Nevo, B., & Derech-Zehavi, A. (1993). The development of the tendency to gossip questionnaire: Construct and concurrent validation for a sample of Israeli college students. *Educational and Psychological Measurement*, 53(4), 973-981. <https://doi.org/10.1177/0013164493053004010>
- Rajačić, A. B., Kišjuhas, A., & Škorić, M. (2020). The sociology of gossip and small talk: A metatheory. *Sociología*, 52(6), 559-577. <https://www.sav.sk/journals/uploads/11301110Bilinovic%20-%20Kisjuhas%20-%20Skoric%206-2020.pdf>
- Rözer, J., Mollenhorst, G., & Poortman, A. R. (2016). Family and friends: Which types of personal relationships go together in a network? *Social Indicators Research*, 127, 809-826. <https://doi.org/10.1007/s11205-015-0987-5>
- Seyfarth, R. M., & Cheney, D. L. (1993). Grooming is not the only regulator of primate social interactions. *Behavioral and Brain Sciences*, 16(4), 717-718. <https://doi.org/10.1017/S0140525X00032593>
- Wu, L. Z., Birtch, T. A., Chiang, F. F., & Zhang, H. (2018). Perceptions of negative workplace gossip: A self-consistency theory framework. *Journal of Management*, 44(5), 1873-1898. <https://doi.org/10.1177/01492063166632057>
- Yan, L., & Zhang, Q. (2021). The study on the influence of workplace gossip on employees' work enthusiasm. *E3S Web of Conferences*, 253, 01024. <https://doi.org/10.1051/e3sconf/202125301024>
- Yue, W., Wu, L., Yang, Z., & Zhai, H. (2015). The antecedents and consequences of workplace negative gossip: from the target's perspective. *Advances in Psychological Science*, 23(4), 702-710. <https://doi.org/10.3724/SP.J.1042.2015.00702>